

Particle in an Infinite Well from an Information Perspective

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In this note, we wish to consider a single particle in an infinite potential well (i.e. one in which there is no probability for the particle to be outside the well in both the classical and quantum views) from the perspective of information that must be measured. We first consider the classical idea of momentum = mv (nonrelativistically). (Our arguments also hold for special relativity.) If one knows rest mass m_0 , then increasing energy means increasing velocity. In general, however, one may have $p = mv_1 = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ etc, so we argue that from a momentum perspective it is not useful to think in terms of m_0 or v , only in terms of p . Secondly, p is proportional to impulse classically, but in the interior of the well, no collisions occur, so we argue that this is also not relevant information, at least in the interior. It is, however, relevant information at the walls where impulse is measured through collision. Thus, we base our analysis on p because this measurement must occur at the walls.

The question then becomes: What is the relevant information associated with different momenta in the well if one does not consider velocity or impulse? We suggest that all that is left is to map momentum into x with respect to information. In other words, a given p number (one dimension) would be described by a set of equally spaced x points due to translational invariance in the well.

To begin, consider a low momentum p_1 , associated with a certain amount of information in x . If one increases this momentum, one retains the information amount of p_1 (because information is not destroyed here, we postulate), but some extra information should appear to indicate that momentum has been increased. Reverse arguments for dropping from a high momentum to a lower one also hold. Thus, a high momentum represents more information than a lower one in x .

As a result, p , a number in one dimension, has been mapped into an interval x of length L . Presumably, information in L would be a set of x points. For high p , there should be more x points. This, however, is not the full picture. In Newtonian mechanics, momentum is conserved as it is in an infinite well potential. Thus, two sets of points in L for p_1 and p_2 should indicate different states. The two sets of x points appear to be vectors so one may take a dot product to see that they represent completely different states, i.e. the two should be orthogonal. Now, the dot product of x points are not orthogonal, but one may map these points to crests and troughs to create sine functions with different periods and these are orthogonal. The period, or rather half-wavelengths are defined as the distance between x points.

Thus, we argue that the quantum mechanical picture for an infinite well follows from classical ideas, but non-relevant information (which would be relevant classically where it is assumed one may measure x and t with infinite resolution) is dropped, leaving a picture in which one may only use information available, i.e. points in x .

Classical Measurements

Classical mechanics assumes that one knows x and t precisely. X , however, is usually measured by bouncing light off of a particle. It has been known for a long time that light has a

wavelength and creates interference patterns. Thus, using light means one cannot know x with complete precision. The precision depends on the wavelength. In fact, it is not clear that one may make any x measurement with complete precision. Newtonian mechanics, however, assumes complete precision because $dx \rightarrow 0$.

Particle in an Infinite Well

We wish to consider the problem of a particle in an infinite well because this scenario represents a particle confined to the well in both the classical and quantum views. We wish to ask: What information is relevant in this problem? This means that we do not include usual information that one would not necessarily measure such as the position and time of the particle.

One piece of information is velocity, but there is also momentum and nonrelativistically:

$$p = mv = m_0 v_0 = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2 = \dots \quad ((1))$$

Thus, we drop rest mass and velocity because different values of these lead to the same momentum, albeit different energies. Momentum cannot be dropped because it is proportional to impulse which occurs at the walls and hence is measured at the walls.

Thus, we first of all suggest that one may describe the problem in terms of momentum. The impulse measurement is the same for $mv = m_1 v_1$. We do no measurements in the interior of the well. Given this condition, one does not know the impulse in the interior either because it is not being measured. All one knows then is that the particle is somewhere within the well and can have different p values.

If this is the only information available, we suggest mapping a p value (i.e. a number in one-dimension) to x points because it seems that this is the only information one has. For a low p , there are a certain number of x points. If one increases p , then we suggest that one cannot lose the existing amount of information, but must augment it because p increases. Thus, we suggest more x points for higher p values.

The Notion of Orthogonality

Thus, p numbers are mapped into sets of x points (like a kind of vector), but with the number of elements in the set (or components in the vector) increasing. One still has no idea which x points to use for a given p . The x points should be equally spaced to translational invariance in the well.

A key idea of classical physics is momentum conservation. The two sets of x points must represent physically different states, i.e. different momenta. If one considers the first x point to be a crest and the second a trough etc, then one may create a sinusoidal pattern. Such patterns are orthogonal for different point spacings, assuming all points are equally spaced. This is reasonable because one has free space inside the well. Thus, orthogonality and periodicity become the key idea for choosing the x points which represent the allowable information if one does no measurements within the well region.

Nonrelativistic Versus Relativistic Considerations

In the above discussion, we have used nonrelativistic considerations, but the arguments should all still hold for special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that a quantum picture arises from considering a description of a particle in an infinite well using only information which must be measured. We suggest that p represents impulse, but only at the walls, so the description should be in terms of p which must be measured at the walls. In the interior one does not measure impulse. Furthermore $p = mv = m_1 v_1$ etc means that different m, v combinations create the same impulse at the wall and should be considered the same if this is the only measurement made. Thus, one has a p -based scenario, but there is no way to measure p in the interior, yet it must represent some set of information.

We suggest that the best one may do is to have p map to a set of x points because one only knows that p is within the well. Different p values represent different x points. Given a low p , one has a certain set of x points, i.e. a certain amount of information. If one increases p , one should increase information, so we suggest more x points. These points should be equally spaced to spatial invariance within the well. Finally, we argue that different p 's are physically distinct and the x points should ensure this is some way. We suggest that the way to achieve this is to have the first x point represent a crest and the second, a trough, etc. This then leads to orthogonality and periodicity in x as a description of the particle in an infinite well if one removes all non-measurable information.